

PREVALENCE AND CORRELATION OF CONVENTIONAL AND NOVEL RISK FACTORS IN CORONARY HEART DISEASE

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Abstract

Coronary heart disease (CHD) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally, with increasing prevalence in developing countries such as Pakistan. While conventional risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and dyslipidemia are well recognized, they do not fully explain the burden of CHD. Novel biomarkers like homocysteine and C-reactive protein (CRP) have emerged as important indicators of cardiovascular risk.

This cross-sectional study was conducted among adults in Faisalabad, Pakistan, to determine the prevalence and correlation of conventional and novel CHD risk factors. Participants were selected through systematic random sampling. Data on demographic, lifestyle, clinical, and biochemical variables were collected through structured questionnaires, physical measurements, and laboratory assays. Fasting blood glucose, lipid profile, homocysteine, and CRP were analyzed.

A total of 530 adults participated, with a mean age of 38.1 ± 13.4 years. The prevalence of hypertension, obesity, diabetes, elevated CRP, and hyperhomocysteinemia was 48.6%, 17.2%, 8.9%, 20.3%, and 41.5%, respectively. Homocysteine showed a significant positive correlation with blood pressure ($p < 0.01$) and dyslipidemia, while CRP was associated with obesity ($p < 0.001$). The addition of homocysteine and CRP to traditional risk assessment improved prediction accuracy for CHD risk.

In conclusion, both conventional and novel risk factors contribute substantially to the CHD burden in Faisalabad. Incorporating novel biomarkers such as homocysteine and CRP may enhance early detection and prevention strategies in high-risk populations.

INTRODUCTION

Coronary heart disease (CHD) is characterized by narrowing or blockage of coronary arteries due to atherosclerosis, leading to reduced blood flow to the heart muscle (1). The condition manifests as myocardial infarction, angina, or sudden cardiac death and remains a major public health issue in Pakistan, where lifestyle transitions and

urbanization have increased exposure to cardiovascular risk factors (2).

Conventional risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, smoking, and obesity are well-established contributors to CHD (3). Hypertension and dyslipidemia accelerate atherosclerotic plaque formation, while diabetes promotes endothelial dysfunction and

thrombosis (4). Obesity and sedentary lifestyles further aggravate these conditions, creating a cumulative risk environment (5).

However, traditional risk models explain only a portion of CHD cases, suggesting the involvement of additional, novel risk markers (6). Biomolecules such as homocysteine, an amino acid linked to endothelial injury and oxidative stress, and C-reactive protein (CRP), a sensitive inflammatory marker, have emerged as independent predictors of cardiovascular disease (7). Elevated homocysteine disrupts vascular integrity, while high CRP levels reflect chronic inflammation associated with plaque instability (8).

In Pakistan, few community-based studies have examined these novel biomarkers alongside conventional risk factors. Understanding their prevalence and interrelationships may enhance cardiovascular risk prediction and inform preventive health strategies. This study, therefore, aims to assess the prevalence and correlation of conventional and novel risk factors of CHD among adults in Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Objectives

- i. To determine the prevalence of conventional risk factors (diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and dyslipidemia) and novel biomarkers (homocysteine and C-reactive protein) associated with coronary heart disease in Faisalabad, Pakistan.
- ii. To assess the correlation between conventional and novel risk factors for coronary heart disease.
- iii. To examine the association between lifestyle factors (diet, physical activity, smoking, and alcohol use) and the identified CHD risk factors.
- iv. To evaluate the overall coronary heart disease risk profile among adults in Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

This community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Faisalabad, Pakistan, to assess the prevalence and correlation of conventional and novel risk factors for coronary heart disease (CHD). Faisalabad, a major industrial city, represents a rapidly urbanizing population at high risk for cardiovascular diseases.

Study Population

Participants included men and women aged 18 years and above who had resided in Faisalabad for at least two years and provided written informed consent. Individuals who were pregnant, physically disabled, or had a debilitating chronic illness were excluded to avoid confounding clinical conditions.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multistage random sampling technique was employed. Thirty urban clusters were selected using the probability proportional to size (PPS) method, followed by systematic household selection. One eligible respondent per household was chosen randomly. The sample size ($n = 530$) was determined using Fisher's formula for cross-sectional studies, assuming a 50% prevalence, 5% precision, 95% confidence level, a design effect of 1.2, and a 5% non-response rate (9).

Data Collection Tools

Data were collected using a pretested structured questionnaire covering demographic, socioeconomic, and lifestyle characteristics including diet, smoking, and physical activity. The questionnaire was translated into Urdu and validated through pilot testing in a similar population before administration.

Anthropometric Measurements

Anthropometric measurements included height, weight, waist, and hip circumference, recorded following WHO (2000) guidelines (10). Height was measured using a Leicester stadiometer, and weight was measured using a calibrated mechanical weighing scale (Tanita BWB-800). Body Mass Index (BMI) and waist-hip ratio (WHR) were computed to assess obesity and central adiposity (11).

Clinical and Physical Assessments

Blood pressure was measured using a calibrated sphygmomanometer after a 10-minute rest. Information on smoking habits, alcohol use, physical activity, and family history of diabetes or CHD was obtained. General clinical examinations were performed by trained medical professionals.

Biochemical Analysis

After an overnight fast of 10–12 hours, 8 mL of venous blood was collected from each participant. Fasting Plasma Glucose was determined using the HemoCue Glucose 201+ analyzer. Lipid Profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides, HDL, LDL) was analyzed enzymatically on a KoneLab 20 autoanalyzer using standard protocols. C-Reactive Protein (CRP) was measured by an immunoturbidimetric assay (NycoCard® CRP) to assess inflammation. Total Plasma Homocysteine, a novel biomarker, was analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). All laboratory analyses were performed under strict internal quality control protocols.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining study objectives and procedures. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, and participants requiring medical attention were referred to local health facilities.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

Data were entered in Microsoft Access and analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as percentages. Associations between categorical variables were tested using the chi-square test, and differences in means were assessed using the independent t-test. Correlations between biochemical markers and conventional risk factors were examined using Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients. Binary logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of CHD. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Demographics

A total of 539 adults [(m: 272 (50.5%); w: 267 (49.5%)] participated in the study. Figure illustrates the distribution of participants by age and sex. The mean age was 38.09 ± 13.4 years.

Distribution of age by sex

Figure 1: Distribution of participants by age and sex

Prevalence of conventional risk factors for coronary heart disease in the study subjects.

Among 536 participants (men: 50.3%, women: 49.7%), diabetes prevalence was 9.1%, similar in men (8.9%) and women (9.4%). IFG affected 2.7%, higher in women (4.1%) than men (1.5%). Most participants (88.2%) had normal glucose, with no significant gender association ($p=0.296$).

Distribution of diabetes by age

Among 520 participants, normal glucose decreased and diabetes increased with age. IFG was highest in the 35–44 years group, while diabetes was most prevalent in those >55 years. A significant positive association was observed between age and blood glucose ($r=0.257$; $p<0.001$).

Figure 2: Distribution of age specific fasting blood glucose concentrations.

Table 1: Distribution of blood pressure by gender

Prevalence of hypertension

Among 520 participants, hypertension was more common in men (57.1%) than women (42.9%). Pre-hypertension affected 33.4% overall, slightly higher in women (51.4%) than men (48.6%) based on WHO and diastolic criteria, while systolic measurements showed higher pre-hypertension in men (58.9% vs. 41.1%).

		Normal		Pre-hypertension		Hypertension	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
*WHO	Men	85	32.9	173	48.6	261	57.1
	Women		57.1		51.4		42.9
Systolic	Men	166	31.9	197	58.9	157	59.2
	Women		58.1		41.1		40.8
Diastolic	Men	108		165	47.3	246	56.1
	Women		40.7		52.7		43.9

*WHO classification (2004) is based on a report on the status of cardiovascular disease in the commonwealth.

Distribution of hypertension by age

When blood pressure was assessed across the five age groups, pre-hypertension was highest in the 25-34 years age group [n=136 (43.4%)] and hypertension highest in the 35-44 years age group [(n=140 (49.3%)). A significant association was observed between hypertension and increasing age (r=0.382; p<0.001).

Figure 3: Age specific distribution of blood pressure

Prevalence of Dyslipidemia

A total of 516 participants (men: 50.8%; women: 49.2%) were assessed for lipid profiles (TC, HDLc, LDLc, TAG). Men had higher TAG levels, with 66.7% showing borderline/high levels (p=0.025). TC and HDLc distributions were similar between sexes; 67.6% had normal TC, 53.1% had low HDLc, and no significant gender associations were observed (TC: p=0.958, HDLc: p=0.736). TAG levels were mostly normal (82.6%), while LDLc levels varied: normal 26.8%, near normal 32.2%, borderline 24.5%, high 11.5%, very high 5%. Women had more near normal and very high LDLc, men more borderline, with no significant gender association.

Table 2: Distribution of lipid profile by gender

	LDL (mmol/L)			TAG (mmol/L)			N	TC (mmol/L)		HDLc (mmol/L)		
	n	Men	Women	n	Men	Women		Men	Women	n	Men	Women
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	274	50.4%	49.6%
Normal	138	55.1%	44.9%	427	48.7%	51.3%	349	50.7%	49.3%	0	0	0
Near Normal	166	47.6%	52.4%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Borderline	126	54.0%	46.0%	48	66.7%	33.3%	109	52.3%	47.7%	222	50.5%	49.5%
High	59	49.2%	50.8%	42	57.1%	42.9%	58	48.3%	51.7%	20	60.0%	40.0%
Very high	26	42.3%	57.7%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Distribution of lipid profile by age

Among 516 participants, age distribution was 18-24 (17.2%), 25-34 (27.1%), 35-44 (27.3%), 45-54 (15.5%), and >55 years (12.8%). LDL cholesterol was highest in the >55 (30.8%) and 45-54 (26.9%) age groups. The 35-44 group showed the highest triglycerides (53.7%) and total cholesterol (33.9%), while the 25-34 and 35-44 groups had the lowest HDL cholesterol (27.1% each).

Table 3: Age-specific distribution of LDL cholesterol and triglycerides

Age group (years)	N	LDLC (mmol/L)					TAG (mmol/L)		
		Optimal	Near Optimal	Borderline	High	Very high	Normal	Borderline	High
18-24	89	23.2%	21.1%	11.1%	10.2%	7.7%	20.2%	4	2.4
	140								
25-34		34.8%	30.1%	23.0%	11.9%	19.2%	30.4%	12.2%	9.8%
35-44	141	28.3%	25.9%	27.8%	32.2%	15.4%	25.2%	22.4%	53.7%
	80								
45-54		8.7%	16.3%	14.3%	27.1%	26.9%	13.6%	30.6%	17.1%
>55	66	5.1%	6.6%	23.8%	18.6%	30.8%	10.6%	30.6%	17.1%

Table 4: Age-specific distribution of total cholesterol and HDL cholesterol

Age group (years)	N	TC (mmol/L)			HDLc (mmol/L)		
		Normal	Borderline	High	Low	Borderline	High
18-24	89	21%	11.90%	5.10%	15.4%	21.2%	4.8%
	140						
25-34		33.3%	14.7%	13.6%	27.1%	27.5%	19.0%
35-44	141	25.6%	29.4%	33.9%	27.1%	26.1%	38.1%
45-54	80	13.2%	18.3%	23.7%	14.3%	15.8%	28.6%
>55	66	6.9%	25.7%	23.7%	16.1%	9.5%	9.5%

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A significant positive association was observed between increasing age and, TC levels ($r=0.315$; $p<0.001$), TAG concentrations ($r=0.275$; $p<0.001$) and LDLc ($r=0.299$; $p<0.001$). An inverse insignificant association was observed between age and HDLc concentrations ($r= -0.051$; $p=0.243$).

Among 537 participants (270 men, 267 women), obesity was more prevalent in women (27.3%) than men (5.9%). In men, 7% were underweight, 57.4% normal, and 29.6% overweight, while in women, 2.6% were underweight, 39.7% normal, and 30.3% overweight. BMI showed a significant positive correlation with age in both men ($r = 0.272$; $p < 0.001$) and women ($r = 0.298$; $p < 0.001$).

Table 5: Distribution of obesity by age group and gender based on body mass index

	Age-group (years)	Underweight (BMI 18.49 and below)	Normal (BMI 18.5 - 24.99)	Overweight (BMI 25.0 - 29.99)	Obesity (BMI 30.0 and above)
		n=19	n=155	n=80	n=16
Male (n=270)	18-24	1.9%	13.7%	1.5%	0.4%
	25-34	1.9%	15.6%	6.7%	1.9%
	35-44	1.1%	16.7%	7.8%	1.5%
	45-54	1.5%	8.1%	5.6%	1.1%
	>55	0.7%	3.3%	8.1%	1.1%
	Total		7.0%	57.4%	29.6%
Female (n=267)		n=7	n=106	n=81	n=73
	18-24	0.4	10.5	4.9	0.4%

25-34	0.7	13.9	7.1	5.7%
35-44	0.4	7.5	9.0	9.7%
45-54	0.4	3.7	5.6	5.9
>55	0.7	4.1	3.7	5.6
Total%	2.6	39.7	30.3	27.3

Prevalence of novel risk factors for coronary heart disease in the study subjects.

Among 503 participants, 72% had normal homocysteine (Hcy) levels (5–15 μmol/L), while 24.4% showed moderate, 2.8% intermediate, and 0.9% severe hyperhomocysteinemia, with a mean concentration of 15.06 ± 11.82 μmol/L (range: 5.47–127.10). Hcy levels were significantly higher in men than women (r = -0.278; p < 0.001) and increased progressively with age (r = 0.237; p < 0.001), particularly among individuals aged 18–54 years.

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Hcy (μmol/L)

Figure 4: Distribution of homocysteine by gender

Table 6: Distribution of Homocysteine by age group

Age grouped (years)	n	Normal (5-15mmol/L) (%)	Moderate (15-30μmol/L) (%)	Intermediate (30-100mmol/L) (%)	Severe (>100mmol/L) (%)
18-24	88	19.9	11.5	0	40
25-34	137	29.6	22.1	20	0
35-44	135	28.5	21.3	20	60
45-54	79	11.9	24.6	40	0
>55	64	10	20.5	20	0
Total (n)	503	361	122	15	5

Distribution of C-reactive protein by gender

Among 535 participants, most (81.6%) had CRP <5 mg/L. Elevated CRP levels were more common in women: 5–10 mg/L (65.2%) and 11–50 mg/L (54.8%). Only 0.3% had CRP >50 mg/L. A significant association was observed between gender and CRP (r=0.100; p=0.021).

Distribution of CRP by sex

Figure 5: Distribution of C-reactive protein concentrations by gender

Distribution of C-reactive protein by age

CRP levels <5 mg/L were most common in the 25-34 (27.6%) and 35-44 (26.4%) age groups. The 35-44 group had the highest 5-10 mg/L CRP (30.8%), while 11-50 mg/L CRP was most frequent in the 25-34 group. A significant positive association was observed between age and CRP ($r=0.102$; $p=0.018$).

Table 7: Distribution of C-reactive protein concentrations by age group

Age grouped (years)	N	< 5mg/L (%)	5-10mg/L (%)	11-50mg/L (%)	>50mg/L (%)
18-24	91	18	12.3	12.5	0
25-34	142	27.6	18.5	28.1	0
35-44	145	26.4	30.8	21.9	100
45-54	87	15.7	20	15.6	0
>55	73	12.3	18.5	21.9	0
Total (n)	538	439	65	32	2

Relationship between conventional and novel risk factors for coronary heart disease.

Relationship between homocysteine and conventional risk factors

The distribution of homocysteine concentrations above $15\mu\text{mol/L}$ amongst the diabetic subjects was equal across gender. Bivariate analysis found no association between Hcy with blood glucose concentrations ($r= -0.012$; $p=0.850$) in both women and men ($r=0.034$; $p=0.590$).

Table 8: Distribution of homocysteine concentrations across blood glucose categories

Hcy conc ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	Women				Men			
	Blood glucose (mmol/L)				Blood glucose (mmol/L)			
n	Normal	IFG	Diabetes	n	Normal	IFG	Diabetes	

Normal (5-15)	195	91.3%	2.6%	6.2%	166	91.6%	0.6%	7.8%
Moderate (15-30)	47	91.5%	0%	8.5%	75	92%	0%	8%
Intermediate (30-100)	4	100%	0%	0%	11	72.7%	27.3%	0%
Severe (>100)	0	0%	0%	0%	4	100%	0%	0%

Among the 486 participants assessed for Hcy concentrations and blood pressure, blood pressure increased with increasing Hcy concentrations in both sexes . A significant association was observed between Hcy levels and increasing blood pressure in men ($r=0.180$; $p=0.005$) and women ($r=0.146$; $p=0.024$). A stronger positive association was observed between Hcy concentrations and systolic blood pressure than with diastolic blood pressure in both men (systolic: $r=0.209$; $p=0.001$ vs. diastolic: $r=0.145$; $p=0.023$) and women (systolic: $r=0.200$; $p=0.002$ vs. diastolic: $r=0.121$; $p=0.061$). The association between Hcy and systolic blood pressure was prominent in the 18-24 age group ($r=0.225$; $p=0.040$).

■	
■	
□	Normal
	Pre-HT
	HT

Figure 6: Distribution of homocysteine among blood pressure categories

Among 497 participants, TC, TAG, and LDLc increased with higher Hcy levels. Significant associations were observed: in women, Hcy with TC ($r=0.135$; $p=0.035$) and LDLc ($r=0.149$; $p=0.020$); in men, Hcy with TAG ($r=0.167$; $p=0.008$). The 35-44 years group showed the strongest positive correlations with LDLc, TAG, and TC, while TAG was inversely associated in those >55 years ($r=-0.335$; $p=0.008$). Hcy was not significantly associated with BMI, but multivariate analysis showed strong associations with blood pressure (AOR 3.062; $p=0.002$) and obesity (AOR 0.146; $p<0.001$).

Table 9: Distribution of homocysteine across the lipid profile

Concentrations in mmol/L		N	Hcy conc (µmol/L)			
			5-15	15-30	30-100	>100
TC	Normal (<5.17)		73.1%	23.1%	3.3%	0.6%
	Borderline (5.17-6.2)		72.4%	21.9%	2.9%	2.9%
	High risk (≥6.2)		63.0%	37.0%	0%	0%
HDLc	Low (≤1.03)		70%	25.5%	3.4%	1.1%
	Borderline (1.04-1.6)		73.4%	23.4%	2.3%	0.9%
	High (>1.6)		84.2%	15.8%	0%	0%
TAG	Normal (≤1.69)	338	74.4%	22.4%	2.7%	0.5%
		105				
	Borderline (1.7-2.25)	54				
		263				
		214				
		19				
		410				
		48				
		39				
		135				
	161					
	120					
	High (2.26-5.6)		59.0%	33.3%	0%	7.7%
LDLc	Optimal (≤ 2.6)		77.8%	20.0%	0.7%	1.5%

	Near Optimal (2.6-3.3)		70.8%	24.8%	4.3%	0%
	Borderline (3.4-4.12)		72.5%	23.3%	4.2%	0%
	High (4.13-4.9)	55	65.5%	27.3%	1.8%	5.5%
	Very high (≥ 4.9)	24	58.3%	41.7%	0%	0%

Table 10: Distribution of homocysteine across various obesity measures

		Hcy concentrations				
		n	5-15 μ mol/L (%)	15-30 μ mol/L (%)	30-100 μ mol/L (%)	>100 μ mol/L (%)
BMI	Underweight	24	33.3	45.8	20.8	0
	Normal	254	78.3	19.3	1.6	0.8
		146				
		52				
	Overweight		66.4	30.1	1.4	2.1
	Obesity grade 1		71.2	23.1	5.8	0
	Obesity grade 2	22	77.3	22.7	0	0
Obesity grade 3	8	62.5	25	12.5	0	

Table 11: Relationship between homocysteine and diabetes, hypertension, obesity and dyslipidaemia

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Fasting blood glucose		
• Normal	Reference	
• IFG	0.605 (0.114 - 3.218)	0.556
• Diabetes	0.777 (0.343 - 1.756)	0.544
Blood pressure		
• Normal	Reference	
• Pre-hypertension	1.961 (0.925 - 4.155)	0.079
• Hypertension	3.062 (1.488 - 6.300)	0.002
Obesity (BMI)		
• underweight	Reference	
• normal	0.105 (0.040 - 0.275)	0.000
• above 25	0.146 (0.055 - 0.390)	0.000
Total cholesterol		
• <5.17mmol/L	Reference	
• borderline (5.17-6.2mmol/L)	0.645 (0.294 - 1.417)	0.275
• High risk(≥ 6.2 mmol/L)	0.701 (0.194 - 2.534)	0.588
High density lipoprotein cholesterol		
• Low ≤ 1.03 mmol/L	Reference	
• Borderline = 1.04-1.6 mmol/L	0.920 (0.572 - 1.479)	0.730
• High > 1.6 mmol/L	0.631 (0.164 - 2.423)	0.502

Triglycerides <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal =<1.69mmol/L • Borderline High= 1.7-2.25mmol/L • High=2.26-5.6mmol/L 	Reference 1.393 (0.677 - 2.863) 1.826 (0.836 - 3.988)	0.368 0.131
Low density lipoprotein cholesterol <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal <=2.6 • Near Optimal (2.6-3.3) • Borderline (3.4-4.12) • High (4.13-4.9) • Very high (>=4.9) 	Reference 1.466 (0.818 - 2.627) 1.465 (0.698 - 3.073) 2.434 (0.787 - 7.525) 3.172 (0.685 - 14.686)	0.199 0.313 0.123 0.140

Relationship between C-reactive protein and conventional risk factors

The distribution of CRP concentrations among the three categories of blood glucose concentration. C-reactive protein concentrations increased with increasing blood glucose concentration. No significant association was observed between CRP and fasting blood glucose concentrations in both genders and neither amongst the various age groups ($p>0.005$).

Table 12: Distribution of C-reactive protein concentrations among blood glucose categories

CRP conc. (mmol/L)	Women				Men			
	n	Blood glucose (mmol/L)			n	Blood glucose (mmol/L)		
		Normal	IFG	Diabetes		Normal	IFG	Diabetes
Normal (<5)	205	91%	2%	7%	230	92%	2%	7%
Moderate (5-10)	44	93%	5%	2%	23	91%	0%	9%
Intermediate (11-50)	17	77%	0%	24%	15	87%	0%	13%
Severe (>50)	0	0%	0%	0%	2	100%	0%	0%

CRP distribution across blood pressure categories was similar between sexes, with no significant association observed ($p>0.05$). CRP showed strong positive correlations with TC ($r=0.69$) and LDLc ($r=0.64$), and a negative correlation with HDLc ($r=-0.61$), but no significant associations were found with lipid concentrations overall.

Table 13: Distribution of CRP at various cholesterol and triglyceride concentrations

		CRP concentration (mmol/L)				
		n	<5	5-10	10-50	>50
TC	<5.17mmol/L	349	83.1%	11.7%	5.2%	0%
	borderline (5.17-6.2mmol/L)	110	74.5%	14.5%	9.1%	1.8%
	High risk(>=6.2mmol/L)	58	81.0%	13.8%	5.2%	0%
HDLc	Low =<1.03mmol/L	274	79%	14.6%	6.6%	0%
	Borderline = 1.04-1.6 mmol/L	223	83.9%	9.9%	5.4%	0.9%
	High >1.6mmol/L	20	85.0%	10.0%	5%	0%

TAG	Normal =<1.69mmol/L	427	81.5%	11.7%	6.8%	0%
	Borderline High= 1.7-2.25mmol/L	49	81.6%	10.2%	4.1%	4.1%
	High=2.26-5.6mmol/L	41	75.6%	24.4%	0%	0%
LDLc	Optimal <=2.6	138	84.1%	10.9%	5.1%	0%
	Near Optimal (2.6-3.3)	167	82.0%	13.2%	4.8%	0%
	Borderline (3.4-4.12)	127	81.1%	11.0%	6.3%	1.6%
	High (4.13-4.9)	58	77.6%	15.5%	6.9%	0%
	Very high (>=4.9)	26	73.1%	15.4%	11.5%	0%

The distribution of CRP and across the obesity categories. A significant positive association was observed between CRP and BMI ($r=0.138$; $p=0.001$) with bivariate analysis. However, multivariate analysis invalidated CRP as an independent predictor of conventional CHD risk factors.

Table 14: Distribution of C-reactive protein at various obesity measures

		CRP concentration (mmol/L)				
			5-10	10-50	>50	
Obesity (BMI)	Underweight	n	3.7	7.4	0	
	Normal	27	10.7	5.0	0	
	Overweight	261	9.3	4.3	1.2	
	Obesity grade 1	162	16.7	11.1	0	
	Obesity grade 2	54	56.5	39.1	4.3	0
	Obesity grade 3	23	10	40	40	20

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Fasting blood glucose		
• Normal	Reference	
• IFG	0.784 (0.129 - 4.750)	0.791
• Diabetes	1.281 (0.555 - 2.959)	0.562
Blood pressure		
• Normal	Reference	
• Pre-hypertension	1.053 (0.504 - 2.202)	0.891
• Hypertension	1.239 (0.619 - 2.478)	0.546
Obesity (BMI)		
• underweight	Reference	
• normal	1.661 (0.436 - 6.327)	0.457
• above 25	2.470 (0.645 - 9.465)	0.187
Total cholesterol		
• <5.17mmol/L	Reference	
• borderline (5.17-6.2mmol/L)	1.703 (0.747 - 3.884)	0.206
• High risk(>=6.2mmol/L)	0.540 (0.124 - 2.357)	0.413

High density lipoprotein cholesterol <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low =<1.03mmol/L Borderline = 1.04-1.6 mmol/L High >1.6mmol/L 	Reference 0.873 (0.530 - 1.439) 0.866 (0.236 - 3.185)	0.595 0.829
Triglycerides <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Normal =<1.69mmol/L Borderline High= 1.7-2.25mmol/L High=2.26-5.6mmol/L 	Reference 0.652 (0.271 - 1.571) 1.130 (0.480 - 2.660)	0.341 0.780
Low density lipoprotein cholesterol <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimal <=2.6 Near Optimal (2.6-3.3) Borderline (3.4-4.12) High (4.13-4.9) Very high (>=4.9) 	Reference 1.040 (0.548 - 1.971) 0.761 (0.326 - 1.773) 1.311 (0.403 - 4.258) 3.214 (0.560 - 18.444)	0.905 0.526 0.653 0.190

Table 15: Relationship between C-reactive protein and diabetes, hypertension, obesity and dyslipidaemia

Relationship between lifestyle attributes (diet, physical activity and exercise, smoking and alcohol) and conventional and novel risk factors for coronary heart disease

Relationship between homocysteine and lifestyle attributes

Homocysteine (Hcy) levels were significantly associated with smoking, alcohol use, walking, and diet (githeri and spinach) (p<0.05). Logistic regression identified consumption of cucumbers, oranges, fried doughnuts, and mutton as additional factors associated with elevated Hcy.

Table 16: Relationship between homocysteine and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Alcohol use	0.664 (0.367- 1.201)	0.175
Physical activity		
Light (e.g. house chores)	Reference	
Moderate (e.g. car washing)	1.582(0.864- 2.894)	0.137
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	1.015 (0.064- 16.152)	0.992
Exercise		
Light (e.g. brisk walking)	Reference	
Moderate (e.g. jogging, skipping rope)	0.649 (0.246- 1.709)	0.381
Heavy (e.g. gym, aerobics)	1.563 (0.942- 2.591)	0.084
Smoking	1.779 (0.903- 3.502)	0.096
Diet		
Doughnuts	0.193 (0.045-0.830)	0.027 0.085
Wheat Bread	2.738 (0.869-8.627)	0.002 0.015
Cucumber	0.218 (0.082 -0.578)	0.052
Oranges	9.632 (1.541 - 60.214)	0.015
Lemons	0.374 (0.139 - 1.007)	
Mutton	0.329 (0.135 - 0.805)	

Relationship between C-reactive protein and lifestyle attributes

Bivariate analysis revealed boiled corn, roasted corn, fresh tilapia, Nile perch, chick peas, green grams, peanuts, ginger and walking to be significantly associated with CRP levels. Multivariate analysis found no positive association between the lifestyle attributes and CRP levels.

Table 17: Regression between C-reactive protein and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Alcohol use	0.602(0.312 - 1.160)	0.129
Physical activity		
Light (house chores)	Reference	
Moderate (car washing)	0.742(0.388 - 1.420)	0.368
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	0.000(0.000)	0.999
Exercise		
Light (brisk walking)	Reference	
Moderate (jogging, skipping rope etc)	0.472(0.170 - 1.312)	0.150
Heavy (Gym, aerobics)	0.491(0.161 - 1.500)	0.212
Smoking	1.543(0.743 - 3.203)	0.245
Diet		
Ripe Banana	6.410(0.990 - 41.496)	0.051

Relationship between diabetes and lifestyle attributes

Bivariate analysis showed diabetes and elevated blood glucose were associated ($p < 0.05$) with consumption of various foods (e.g., white maize, bread, brown rice, doughnuts, beef, sugar, spices), smoking, and physical inactivity. Regression analysis identified wheat bread consumption as protective against diabetes ($p < 0.05$).

Table 18: Relationship between diabetes and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Alcohol use	1.299(0.474 - 3.564)	0.611
Physical activity		
Light (e.g. house chores)	Reference	
Moderate (e.g. car washing)	1.844(0.778 - 4.368)	0.164
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	1.418 (0.000)	0.999
Exercise		
Light (e.g. brisk walking)	Reference	
Moderate (e.g. jogging, skipping rope)	8.742(0.000)	0.997
Heavy (e.g. gym, aerobics)	0.591(0.124 - 2.801)	0.507
Smoking	0.522(0.196 - 1.391)	0.194
Sex	0.830(0.365 - 1.885)	0.656
Diet		
Wheat Bread	0.048(0.002- 0.976)	0.048

Relationship between hypertension and lifestyle attributes

Factors found to be associated ($p < 0.05$) with presence of hypertension were alcohol use, smoking, physical inactivity and lack of exercise, and consumption of millet, white and brown sugar. Regression analysis revealed exercise, consumption of fruits, vegetables and pulses as some of the factors inversely associated with occurrence of hypertension.

Table 19: Relationship between hypertension and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)		p -value
Alcohol use	1.155	.702 1.899	0.571
Physical activity	Reference		
Light (e.g. house chores)	Reference		
Moderate (e.g. car washing)	0.946	(0.553 - 1.620)	0.841
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	0.000	(0.000 -)	0.999
Exercise	Reference		
Light (e.g. brisk walking)	0.868	(0.439 - 1.715)	0.683
Moderate (e.g. jogging, skipping rope)	0.868	(1.191 - 5.802)	0.683
Heavy (e.g. gym, aerobics)	2.628		0.017
Smoking	1.013	.549 1.868	0.967
Diet	(1.446 - 14.351)		
Cucumber	4.555	(2.199 - 39.972)	0.010
Indigenous Vegetables	9.376	(0.035 - 0.526)	0.002
Eggplant	0.136	(1.360 - 51.651)	0.004
Mangoes	8.380	(1.063 - 8.224)	0.022
Passion	2.957	(0.013 - 0.749)	0.038
White Sugar	0.097	(0.073 - 0.864)	0.025
Brown sugar	0.251	(0.154 - 1.034)	0.028
Intestines	0.399	(1.267 - 19.782)	0.059
Peanuts	5.006		0.022

4.5.5 Relationship between dyslipideamia and lifestyle attributes

Total cholesterol was elevated with consumption of maize meal, bread, goat meat, and fried dough, but lower with fruits and vegetables (carrots, sukuma, papaya, mangoes, oranges, avocado, bananas, passion fruit). Low HDLc was observed in consumers of roasted corn and white rice, while TAG was low with wheat bread and English yam but elevated with fried dough, corn, and sweet potatoes. Regression analysis identified dietary factors as the main contributors to dyslipidemia.

Obesity and Lifestyle

BMI was higher among consumers of maize meal, white rice, and chapatti, and lower in those consuming yams, vegetables (pepper, spinach, cucumber, lettuce, eggplant, indigenous greens), fruits (apples, lemons, pears), chicken, and legumes. Regression analysis indicated dietary factors as the primary determinants of BMI.

Table 20: Relationship between dyslipideamia and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI); p-value	
	HDLc	LDLc
Alcohol use	1.534 (0.961 - 2.448); p= 0.073	0.606 (0.322 1.142) p=0.121
Physical activity	Reference	
Light (house chores)	Reference	Reference
Moderate (car washing)	0.924 (0.568 - 1.505); p=0.752	0.876 (0.450 - 1.705); p=0.697
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	1.414 (0.086 - 23.257); p=0.808	4.2668 (0.000); p=0.999
Exercise	Reference	
Light (brisk walking)	Reference	Reference
Moderate (e.g. jogging, biking)	1.229 (0.661 - 2.285); p=0.514	0.577 (0.254 - 1.312); p=0.190
Heavy (e.g. Gym, aerobics)	0.886 (0.451 - 1.743); p=0.727	1.189 (0.371 - 3.810); p=0.771

Smoking	0.741 (0.416-1.321); <i>p</i> =0.310	0.510 (0.257 - 1.014); <i>p</i> =0.055
Diet	Roasted Corn: 0.066(0.016 - 0.267); <i>p</i> <0.001 Pepper: 0.265 (0.103 - 0.681); <i>p</i> =0.006 White sugar: 0.079(0.007 - 0.946); <i>p</i> =0.045 Wine: 0.241(0.062 - 0.933); <i>p</i> =0.039.	White bread: 0.153(0.032 - 0.739); <i>p</i> =0.020 Chick peas: 6.218 (1.838 - 21.039); <i>p</i> =0.003 Lemons: 4.342(1.026 - 18.380); <i>p</i> =0.046 White sugar: 0.125(0.020 - 0.780); <i>p</i> =0.026
	TAG	TC
Alcohol use	0.788 (0.345 - 1.798); <i>p</i> =0.571	0.579 (0.281 - 1.192); <i>p</i> =0.138
Physical activity		
Light (house chores)	Reference	Reference
Moderate (car washing)	1.259 (0.561 - 2.823); <i>p</i> =0.577	1.140 (0.546 - 2.381); <i>p</i> =0.727
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	2.4308 (0.000); <i>p</i> =0.999	2.030 (0.000); <i>p</i> =0.999
Exercise		
Light (brisk walking)	Reference	Reference
Moderate (e.g. jogging, biking)	0.544 (0.178 - 1.667); <i>p</i> =0.287	2.081 (0.509 - 8.510); <i>p</i> =0.308
Heavy (e.g. Gym, aerobics)	0.390 (0.112 - 1.351); <i>p</i> =0.137	0.312 (0.113 - 0.867); <i>p</i> =0.026
Smoking	0.769 (0.309 - 1.912); <i>p</i> =0.572	0.666 (0.299 - 1.483); <i>p</i> =0.320
Diet	Sweet potatoes: 0.097(0.017-0.550); <i>p</i> =0.008	Roasted Corn: 17.1681(0.250 - 235.790); <i>p</i> =0.033 Wheat Bread: 0.112(0.016 - 0.802); <i>p</i> =0.029 Sweet Potatoes: 0.081(0.012 - 0.555); <i>p</i> =0.011 Pepper: 9.634(1.855 - 50.019); <i>p</i> =0.007 Chicken: 0.102(0.018 - 0.590); <i>p</i> =0.011

Table 21: Relationship between obesity and lifestyle attributes

Risk factors	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p -value
Alcohol use	1.448 (0.890 - 2.357)	0.136
Physical activity		
Light (e.g. house chores)	Reference	
Moderate (e.g. car washing)	0.969 (0.582 - 1.613)	0.904
Heavy (e.g. farming, masonry)	1.247 (0.080 - 19.432)	0.875
Exercise		
Light (e.g. brisk walking)	Reference (0.551 - 2.080)	
Moderate (e.g. jogging, biking)	1.070 (0.555 - 2.520)	0.841
Heavy (e.g. gym, aerobics)	1.183	0.664
Smoking	1.035 (0.574 - 1.866)	0.910
Diet		
Boiled Corn	0.244 (0.074 - 0.803)	0.020
Wheat Bread	4.410 (1.155 - 16.840)	0.030
Pigeon peas	3.219 (1.320 - 7.852)	0.010

Contribution of Homocysteine to CHD Risk Assessment

The Hcy assay showed <50% sensitivity for obesity, hypertension, diabetes, and lipid abnormalities, but >50% specificity in both sexes. Its negative predictive value for diabetes exceeded 90%, though the positive predictive value was low.

Table 22: Sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of homocysteine in relation to conventional CHD risk markers

Contribution of C-reactive protein to CHD risk assessment

	Gender	Lipid Profile						
		BMI (%)	Hypertension (%)	Diabetes (%)	HDLc (%)	LDLc (%)	TC (%)	TAG (%)
Sensitivity	Men	35.3	41.4	31.6	39.2	38.5	44.8	54.2
	Women	26.2	25.3	29.4	21	34.1	28	25
Specificity	Men	74.3	81.5	65.4	81.8	70.3		68.8
	Women	84	87.3	79.1	87.5	86.9		79.5
PPV	Men	33.3	66.6	6.6	60.2	17	14.8	14.6
	Women	7.9	52.1	9.6	52.9	27.5	13.5	7.7
NPV	Men	65.9	13.8	91.6	5.4	31.1	66.3	83
	Women	45.6	25.4	91.3	3.7	27.7	71.7	87.9
							64	
							82.5	

The specificity of CRP to obesity, hypertension, diabetes and the lipid parameters was greater than 80% in both men and women. The NPV of CRP to diabetes was greater than 90% and the PPV to HDLc greater than 60%.

Table 23: Sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of C-reactive protein in relation to CHD risk markers

	Gender	Lipid Profile						
		BMI (%)	Hypertension (%)	Diabetes (%)	HDLc (%)	LDLc (%)	TC (%)	TAG (%)
Sensitivity	Men	41.2	15.3	21.1	17.3	12.5	7.1	16.7
	Women	35.2	27.7	26.3	26.5	35.6	31	33.3
Specificity	Men	86.5	85.7	85.4	83.3	84.4	86.4	87
	Women	81.3	84.2	77.6	87.5	82.3	79.7	75.9
PPV	Men	17.5	63.9	10	61.5	13.1	5.4	10.5
	Women	41	52.5	8.2	60	26.7	15	9.8
NPV	Men	57.5	10.6	91.7	4.4	28.6	68	80.1
	Women	41.8	24	91.2	3.6	26.4	71	86.1

Among 330 women, the 10-year risk of MI or CHD increased with age, with most (67.3%) having <1% risk. Risk gradually rose across age groups, with a small proportion exceeding 10%.

Among 163 men, the 10-year CHD risk also increased with age. About one-third (33.1%) had <1% risk, while higher-risk categories were more represented than in women, with a few exceeding 30%.

Table 24: Distribution of 10 year risk of coronary heart disease among women

Age group (years)	n	FRAMINGHAM RISK TABLES FOR WOMEN													
		10 YEAR RISK OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION OR CORONARY HEART DISEASE DEATH %													
		<1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	11	14	17	
20-34	137	98.5%	1.5%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
35-39	55	87.3%	12.7%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
40-44	37	72.9%	18.9%	5.4%	2.7%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
45-49	35	34.3%	42.9%	8.6%	-	5.7%	2.9%	2.9%	-	2.9%	-	-	-		
50-54	41	41.5%	-	19.5%	9.8%	12.5%	7.3%	4.9%	-	4.9%	-	-	-		
55-59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
60-64	13	-	15.4%	-	30.8%	15.4%	15.4%	7.7%	-	7.7%	7.7%	-	-		
65-69	4	-	-	-	25%	25%	-	-	-	25%	25%	-	-		
70-74	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.5%	-	-	37.5%	37.5%	12.5%		
75-79	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		

Table 25: Distribution of 10 year risk of coronary heart disease among men

Age group (years)	n	FRAMINGHAM RISK TABLES FOR MEN															
		10 YEAR RISK OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION OR CORONARY HEART DISEASE DEATH %															
		<1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	16	20	25	≥30
20-34	64	81.3%	15.6%	-	-	1.6%	-	1.6%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
35-39	22	9.1%	59.1%	18.2%	-	-	-	4.5%	-	4.5%	-	-	-	-	4.5%	-	
40-44	26	-	23.1%	23.1%	19.2%	11.5%	19.2%	-	-	3.8%	-	-	-	-	-	-	
45-49	11	-	9.1%	18.2%	9.1%	18.2%	-	18.2%	-	18.2%	-	-	9.1%	-	-	-	
50-54	27	-	-	-	3.7%	3.7%	3.7%	18.5%	-	18.5%	-	37.0%	-	14.8%	-	-	
55-59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
60-64	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.5%	-	12.5%	-	-	37.5%	37.5%	
65-69	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20%	-	-	-	20%	40%	

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																	%
70-74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
75-79	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

DISCUSSION

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is now a major health concern in developing countries, including Pakistan, where it contributes significantly to premature mortality and economic burden. Rapid urbanization, dietary transitions, and sedentary lifestyles have intensified exposure to cardiovascular risk factors. Traditional risk markers such as hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and dyslipidemia are well established, yet they do not fully account for the observed rise in coronary heart disease (CHD). The addition of novel biomarkers such as homocysteine (Hcy) and C-reactive protein (CRP) may enhance risk prediction and improve preventive strategies.

In this study, hypertension, obesity, and diabetes were prevalent among adults in Faisalabad, with rates comparable to other urban populations in South Asia. Hypertension emerged as the leading contributor to overall CHD risk, consistent with findings from regional studies (12). The observed positive correlation between blood pressure and advancing age emphasizes the need for early detection and lifestyle interventions among middle-aged adults. The prevalence of diabetes also aligned with the increasing burden seen in urban Pakistani populations, where rising obesity and dietary changes contribute to metabolic syndrome.

Gender differences in lipid profile were evident, with men showing higher triglyceride (TAG) levels and women exhibiting higher rates of obesity. These findings mirror global observations where hormonal differences, pregnancy, and dietary patterns influence lipid metabolism in women. Dyslipidemia particularly elevated total cholesterol (TC) and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDLc) remains a central component of CHD risk in this population.

The study found that hyperhomocysteinemia and elevated CRP were prevalent, suggesting their potential utility in refining CHD risk assessment. Homocysteine showed significant associations with hypertension, dyslipidemia, and body mass index (BMI), indicating its contribution to endothelial dysfunction and vascular damage. These findings align with prior reports that elevated homocysteine impairs endothelial nitric

oxide synthesis, leading to oxidative stress and arterial stiffness (13, 14).

CRP, an acute-phase inflammatory marker, was positively associated with obesity and age, supporting its role as an indicator of low-grade chronic inflammation linked to atherosclerosis. However, CRP did not correlate strongly with fasting glucose or lipid fractions, which may suggest that inflammation contributes to CHD risk independently of metabolic parameters.

Lifestyle habits such as diet, smoking, alcohol consumption, and physical inactivity were closely linked with conventional and novel CHD risk markers. High intake of refined carbohydrates, fried foods, and red meat was associated with elevated BMI, blood glucose, and lipid levels. Conversely, regular consumption of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains showed protective effects, consistent with global evidence that plant-based diets lower inflammatory markers and improve lipid metabolism.

Physical inactivity emerged as a significant contributor to elevated blood pressure and dyslipidemia. Although walking was the most common form of exercise reported, its frequency and duration may not have been sufficient to yield cardiovascular benefits. These findings emphasize the need for structured community-based programs promoting physical activity and healthy dietary practices.

The coexistence of elevated homocysteine and CRP with traditional risk factors underscores the multifactorial nature of CHD. While both markers demonstrated high specificity and negative predictive value, their sensitivity was modest, suggesting they may be better suited for risk refinement rather than primary diagnosis. The combined assessment of Hcy and CRP with conventional risk factors could improve early risk stratification, particularly among individuals categorized as intermediate-risk by traditional models.

Hyperhomocysteinemia's strong correlation with hypertension and dyslipidemia suggests that metabolic and inflammatory pathways intersect in CHD pathogenesis. CRP's independent association with obesity further supports the

inflammatory hypothesis of atherosclerosis, where adipose-derived cytokines sustain systemic inflammation.

The findings indicate that incorporating novel biomarkers such as Hcy and CRP into CHD risk models could marginally enhance predictive accuracy. However, population-specific thresholds need to be validated for the Pakistani context. Interventions focusing on weight control, blood pressure regulation, and nutritional supplementation with folate, vitamin B6, and B12 may help reduce homocysteine levels and mitigate CHD risk.

Public health strategies should prioritize multifactorial screening, combining traditional risk assessment with emerging biomarkers to identify high-risk individuals earlier. Moreover, localized health education emphasizing smoking cessation, dietary moderation, and regular exercise remains critical to curb the growing CVD epidemic in Pakistan.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that both conventional and novel biomarkers contribute significantly to CHD risk among adults in Faisalabad. Hypertension and dyslipidemia remain predominant, while elevated homocysteine and CRP provide additional insight into underlying metabolic and inflammatory mechanisms. The integration of these biomarkers into clinical practice could enhance early risk detection and prevention efforts. Future research should focus on longitudinal validation of these findings and cost-effective community interventions to reduce the overall burden of CHD in Pakistan.

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